

Creating Regulatory Compliant ICOs in the Face a Changing Global Landscape

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

An introduction into the overall environment, both historically and at present, with respect to the issuance of security based Tokens as Cryptocurrency.

2. Aim

To create a compliant rich environment in various economic zones and / or jurisdictions to allow the free flow of Tokens globally without regulatory impediment.

3. Material and methods

A study was conducted to review various federal securities law exemptions and regulatory compliance requirements across key capital jurisdictions to evaluate the process of creating a security that would meet the approval of regulators and satisfy the Know Your Client (“KYC”) and Anti-Money Laundering (“AML”) regulatory provisions, while creating a Token, or altcoin, that could be accepted in the digital environment. Although some exemptions already potentially existed for Accredited Investors, the study also undertook to review opportunities related to the use of General Solicitation in an offering of Tokens.

4. Results

At the time of writing, the numerous methods were still under review, but it was recommended that the optimal initial approach would be to qualify and register for the use of an exemption for the cryptocurrency of a bone-fide business provided in a Regulation A+, Tier II offering pursuant to the Securities Act of 1933. This methodology would provide regulatory oversight and approval, ongoing transparency, and limit liability through full and fair disclosure. A Regulation A+, Tier II would limit the ICO to a capital raise of no more than USD \$50 Million per year. This offering could, potentially, be preceded by a Private Placement using the Regulation D, Rule 506(c) exemption if the two offerings properly structured to avoid being integrated under federal securities laws.

February 3, 2018

5. Conclusions

Our conclusion, based on a successful outcome of the Regulation A+, Tier II process will provide opportunities for approved ICOs to comply with federal Securities Law and Regulatory requirements in the United States. It is recommended that upon becoming effective, the Issuer should then apply to each subsequent jurisdiction, allowing the ICO and potentially, the security, to be recognized and approved in those jurisdictions.

6. Keywords

ICO; Tokens; Fintech, Cryptocurrency. Regulation A+, Tier II